

Replication package for “The Impact of AI Coding Assistants on Software Engineering: A Longitudinal Study”

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1 Study Instrument

1.1 Questionnaire Items

Table 1: Questionnaire items

ID	Item	Q1/Q2	Scale
Screening and Context			
Q1.1	Are you currently working professionally in software engineering?	Q1	Yes/No
Q2.1	Are you currently using an AI coding assistant?	Both	Single choice ^a
Q2.5	In which industry is the company you work for primarily operating?	Both	Single choice
Q3.1	Which AI coding assistants are you currently using the most?	Both	Multi-select ^b
Q3.2	How often are you using AI coding assistants while building software?	Both	Likert (frequency)
Q3.3*	What was your initial impression of using an AI coding assistant?	Q1	Likert (impression)
Q3.3*	If you could no longer use an AI coding assistant, how would you feel?	Q2	Likert (disappointment)
Q3.5	What concerns do you have about using AI coding assistants in your workflow?	Both	Ranking ^c
Task Focus Shifts			
Q3.4	When using an AI coding assistant, do you feel you spend more or less time on the following software engineering tasks?	Both	–
Q3.4.1	Designing	Both	Likert (time)
Q3.4.2	Writing code	Both	Likert (time)
Q3.4.3	Refactoring code	Both	Likert (time)
Q3.4.4	Reviewing code	Both	Likert (time)
Q3.4.5	Testing	Both	Likert (time)
Q3.4.6	Debugging	Both	Likert (time)
Q3.6	In what ways has using an AI coding assistant changed your workflow?	Both	Open-ended
Developer Experience and Productivity			
Q4.1	How has your productivity changed since using an AI coding assistant?	Both	Likert (change)
Q4.2	How does using an AI coding assistant affect the following aspects of your Developer Experience?	Both	–
Q4.2.1	Feedback loops ^d	Both	Likert (change)
Q4.2.2	Cognitive load ^d	Both	Likert (change)
Q4.2.3	Flow state ^d	Both	Likert (change)
Q4.3*	Can you describe a specific instance where an AI coding assistant either significantly helped or hindered your work?	Q1	Open-ended
Q4.3*	Have you experienced any unexpected benefits or challenges from using an AI coding assistant? If so, can you describe a specific instance?	Q2	Open-ended
Skill Development and Self-Efficacy			
Q5.1	Has using an AI coding assistant affected your ability to learn and improve your coding skills?	Both	Likert (likelihood)

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ID	Item	Q1/Q2	Scale
Q5.2	Please indicate how much more or less you agree with each of the following statements regarding your confidence in building software when using an AI coding assistant:	Both	–
Q5.2.1	I will be able to achieve most of the goals that I have set for myself. ^e	Both	Likert (comparative agreement)
Q5.2.2	When facing difficult tasks, I am certain that I will accomplish them. ^e	Both	Likert (comparative agreement)
Q5.2.3	In general, I think that I can obtain outcomes that are important to me. ^e	Both	Likert (comparative agreement)
Q5.2.4	I believe I can succeed at most any endeavour to which I set my mind. ^e	Both	Likert (comparative agreement)
Q5.2.5	I will be able to successfully overcome many challenges. ^e	Both	Likert (comparative agreement)
Q5.2.6	I am confident that I can perform effectively on many different tasks. ^e	Both	Likert (comparative agreement)
Q5.2.7	Compared to other people, I can do most tasks very well. ^e	Both	Likert (comparative agreement)
Q5.2.8	Even when things are tough, I can perform quite well. ^e	Both	Likert (comparative agreement)
Q5.3	In what ways has using an AI coding assistant influenced your coding skills and software engineering practices?	Both	Open-ended
Prompt Engineering Perceptions			
Q6.1	How important do you think prompt engineering will be for software engineers in the future? ^f	Both	Likert (importance)
Q6.2	To what extent do you agree that prompt engineering will replace some traditional coding skills? ^f	Both	Likert (agreement)
Q6.3*	How do you think software engineers should develop their prompt engineering skills, and what resources or methods would be most helpful?	Q1	Open-ended
Q6.3*	Has your approach to prompt engineering evolved over the last six months? If so, how and why?	Q2	Open-ended
Demographics			
Q7.1	Gender	Q1	Single choice
Q7.2	Age	Q1	Single choice
Q7.3	Years of software engineering experience	Q1	Single choice
Q7.4	Self-reported expertise level (Dreyfus model)	Q1	Single choice
Q7.5	Primary role	Both [†]	Single choice
Q7.6	Primary programming language	Both [†]	Single choice
Q7.7	Industry	Both [†]	Single choice
Q7.8	Company size	Both [†]	Single choice
Q7.9	Company headquarters location	Both [†]	Single choice
Q7.10	Country of residence	Both [†]	Single choice
Open Reflections			
Q8.2	What advice would you give to someone just starting their software engineering career in the age of AI?	Both	Open-ended
Q8.3	As the field of software engineering continues to evolve, what should engineers focus on to stay adaptable and thrive?	Both	Open-ended
Q8.4	Is there anything else you think we should know?	Both	Open-ended

Notes:

* Items with different wording between Q1 and Q2.

[†] In Q2, demographic items were only displayed if participants indicated their details had changed.

^a Options: Yes (only at work); Yes (only on personal projects); Yes (both at work and on personal projects); No.

^b Q1 offered 9 tools; Q2 offered 23 tools reflecting market evolution. Both included an “Other” option.

^c Concerns: Quality; Readability; Maintainability; Security; Dependency; Learning curve; Other.

- ^d Developer experience dimensions from the DevEx framework [1]. Definitions provided to participants in Section 1.3.1.
- ^e Self-efficacy items adapted from the New General Self-Efficacy Scale (NGSE) [2]. Participants indicated how much *more or less* they agreed with each statement when using an AI coding assistant.
- ^f Definition of prompt engineering provided to participants in Section 1.3.2.

1.2 Response Scales

Table 2: Response scales used in the questionnaire

Scale Type	Response Options
Likert (time)	Much less; Somewhat less; About the same; Somewhat more; Much more
Likert (change)	Much worse; Somewhat worse; About the same; Somewhat better; Much better
Likert (agreement)	Strongly disagree; Somewhat disagree; Neither agree nor disagree; Somewhat agree; Strongly agree
Likert (comparative agreement)	Much less; Somewhat less; About the same; Somewhat more; Much more
Likert (importance)	Not at all important; Slightly important; Moderately important; Very important; Extremely important
Likert (likelihood)	Definitely not; Probably not; Might or might not; Probably yes; Definitely yes
Likert (impression)	Extremely negative; Somewhat negative; Neither positive nor negative; Somewhat positive; Extremely positive
Likert (disappointment)	Not at all disappointed; Slightly disappointed; Moderately disappointed; Very disappointed; Extremely disappointed
Likert (frequency)	Never; Once a week; 2–3 times a week; 4–6 times a week; Daily

1.3 Construct Definitions Provided to Participants

1.3.1 Developer Experience Dimensions

- **Feedback loops:** The speed and effectiveness with which you receive and act on feedback during development.
- **Cognitive load:** The mental effort required to complete your development tasks.
- **Flow state:** The extent to which you can work seamlessly and maintain concentration without interruptions.

1.3.2 Prompt Engineering

Prompt engineering, in the context of AI coding assistants, involves crafting precise and effective instructions or prompts to guide the AI in generating accurate code or providing helpful suggestions. It requires understanding how to communicate with the AI to optimise its responses and improve coding efficiency.

1.4 Key Differences Between Questionnaires

Table 3: Key differences between Q1 and Q2

Item	Questionnaire 1	Questionnaire 2
Q3.1	9 AI tools listed	23 AI tools listed
Q3.3	“What was your initial impression of using an AI coding assistant?”	“If you could no longer use an AI coding assistant, how would you feel?”
Q4.3	“...significantly helped or hindered your work?”	“...unexpected benefits or challenges...”
Q6.3	“How do you think software engineers should develop their prompt engineering skills...”	“Has your approach to prompt engineering evolved over the last six months?”
Demographics	Full demographic questions	Only displayed if participant indicated changes

2 AI Coding Assistants

Table 4: AI coding assistants used by participants at Q1 ($n = 158$) and Q2 ($n = 101$)

Tool	Q1	Q2	Note
GitHub Copilot	110	61	
ChatGPT	111	59	
Claude	23	36	
Cursor	26	29	
Gemini	6	29	
Microsoft Copilot	7	20	
v0.dev	3	8	
Claude Code	0	11	New at Q2
Perplexity	3	5	
JetBrains AI Assistant	1	6	
Windsurf	0	7	New at Q2
AWS CodeWhisperer	4	2	
Sourcegraph Cody	2	2	
Codeium	3	0	Dropped at Q2
Tabnine	3	0	Dropped at Q2
Continue.dev	2	1	
Bolt.new	1	2	
Gemini Code Assist	2	0	Dropped at Q2
Databricks Assistant	1	1	
Aria	1	1	
Custom CLI Assistant	1	1	
Cline	0	2	New at Q2
Lovable	0	2	New at Q2
Roo Code	0	2	New at Q2
Aider	1	0	Dropped at Q2
Groq	1	0	Dropped at Q2
Google Vertex AI	1	0	Dropped at Q2
Fitten Code	1	0	Dropped at Q2
phind.com	1	0	Dropped at Q2
OpenAI Codex	1	0	Dropped at Q2
Glean	1	0	Dropped at Q2
Supermaven	1	0	Dropped at Q2
OpenWebUI	1	0	Dropped at Q2
GitLab Duo	1	0	Dropped at Q2
Grok	0	1	New at Q2
Ollama	0	1	New at Q2
Trae	0	1	New at Q2

3 Software and Packages

Table 5: R packages used for data analysis (R version 4.4.2)

Category	Package (Version)	Primary Purpose
Data Processing	tidyverse (2.0.0)	Data manipulation, joining Q1/Q2 datasets, and visualisation (includes ggplot2).
Statistical Modelling	lme4 (1.1.37) lmerTest (3.1.3) ordinal (2023.12.4.1) effectsize (1.0.1) psych (2.5.6)	Mixed-effects models for paired Q1/Q2 responses. Significance tests for mixed model comparisons. Cumulative link models for ordinal Likert responses. Cohen's d and rank biserial correlation effect sizes. Cronbach's alpha for NGSE self-efficacy scale.
Model Diagnostics	broom (1.0.8) broom.mixed (0.2.9.6)	Tidying model outputs for result tables. Tidying mixed-effects model outputs.
Visualisation	likert (1.3.5) ggalluvial (0.12.5) patchwork (1.3.0) gridExtra (2.3)	Diverging stacked bar charts for Likert responses. Sankey diagrams for tool adoption changes. Combining multiple plots into single figures. Additional plot arrangement utilities.

All packages available from CRAN (<https://cran.r-project.org>).

References

- [1] A. Noda, M.-A. Storey, N. Forsgren, and M. Greiler, “DevEx: What Actually Drives Productivity: The developer-centric approach to measuring and improving productivity,” *Queue*, vol. 21, no. 2, pp. Pages 20:35–Pages 20:53, May 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3595878>
- [2] G. Chen, S. M. Gully, and D. Eden, “Validation of a New General Self-Efficacy Scale,” *Organizational Research Methods*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 62–83, Jan. 2001. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1177/109442810141004>